

Ict Is An Integral Strategy For Crimes Prevention And Detection

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Abstract

Over the years, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has turned our cultures and has been impossible in the past, into an essential part of one's existence. And over half of civilization in the world is digitally connected, and the direction it is moving would grow more. In India, for example, there is a transformation in the application of ICT in almost all disciplines. ICT, though, not only offers advantages but at the same time has risks in the context of cybercrime. Today, cybercrime is growing as a significant global threat in cyberspace. It affects all stakeholders from agencies, business sectors, civil society organizations, and even individual citizens. ICT and other emerging tools are now a valuable resource for reacting to criminals, intervening in policing hotspots, addressing serious offenses, tracking personnel morale, and several other tasks. Technologies such as CCTV, ICT tools, heat control, biometrics, GPS tracking, Web and telephone services are used for the deterrence, identification, analysis, and prosecution of violence in the law enforcement and defense industries. The text suggested that a range of strategies for identifying and stopping crime based on the usage of ICT-related devices such as CCTV, GPS, surveillance systems, etc. could be widely implemented.

Keywords: *Crime Detection, Crime Prevention, GPS, ICT, CCTV, GIS.*

Introduction

ICT and other emerging tools are now a valuable resource for reacting to threats, intervening in policing hotspots, addressing serious offenses, tracking personnel morale, and many other tasks [1]. Technologies such as surveillance cameras, data gathering systems, heat sensors, facial recognition, GPS tracking, and Internet and telecommunications systems are used to detect, investigate, prosecute, and prevent crime in law enforcement. As was the case in the middle of the 20th century, technology is beginning to change the existence of the security forces and has an impact on the management as well as delivery of state services (Nunn, 2013) [2], [3], [1]. Emerging models of the 21st Century call for precise real-time information on strategic planning, problem analysis, deployment judgments, society interface, inter-organizational interaction, accountability, threat detection and several other operations [1], [2], [3].

The usage of technology by the police in England has significantly improved the way the police represent and defend the public for the better. The mission of the police service in England has been, and will still be, both to solve a crime and to seek and deter it from occurring [2], [4], [4]. The way the security forces investigate crimes has been revolutionized by the technology improvements that have become available to the police. The police use ICT to assist in the monitoring of road traffic, where they can watch traffic images and direct them to incidents on the ground through the use of CCTV. The London Metropolitan Police is one of the biggest Surveillance systems in the country. This tracks the M25 and all highways within and outside Westminster, along with the main roads in central London (London Assembly, 2016) [2]. Western Australia Police have reduced crime through the use of predictive analytics and GPS maps which show crime hotspots in the state. By using business intelligence (BI) it has been able to build up a picture of crimes committed over the past five years. The police have combined data from other government agencies to identify areas of social disadvantage.

Bus routes and CCTV data have also been overlaid on to the map. Major roads and CCTV data have been supplemented on the map (Farrell, Tseloni, Mailley & Tilley, 2013) [2], [5].

The Australian Police use information to assign crossings to selected locations to increase response times when a crime occurs. The police are analyzing social media through text mining. Crime investigators used to devote two hours a day looking at the prior day's papers. The code skimmed all the collections from the past night, so it takes 30 seconds in fact, the police are also sending alerts through Twitter or Facebook to individuals who have coordinated big groups warning them that the group is being watched. In the US, most police departments use GPS technologies of their crime-prevention and crime-fighting strategies (White, 2014) [2].

In its capacity to track people and cars reliably, this system offers a variety of innovative law enforcement approaches. PS-based law enforcement tools may be employed in the following ways: emergency response, patrol control, person and car monitoring, and gunshot detection. In most developing countries, there is the main database with information of all residents and connections to other systems, such as the automobile registry database maintained at the Drivers Vehicle Licensing Authority and another strong machine operating the Electronic Fingerprint Recognition Program. This automated program aims to monitor and prevent crime [1], [2].

The discussion would focus on how creative ICT will play a part in mobilizing societies against abuse and crime and supporting critical intervention mechanisms to enhance service quality. Memeza, working with the Center for Public Service Innovation, SAPS, and the Innovation Hub, has developed a Community Safety Alarm system that enables SAPS to link directly to community families and offices while capturing important crime-related information [6]. A trial was conducted in 2015 in Diep Loot, Johannesburg, where 600 Memeza Community Alarm Systems were installed. By September 2015, national crime statistics suggest that Diep Loot was the only township in Gauteng with a 9 percent decrease in murder rates and a 26% reduction in sexual abuse offenses [6].

The Concepts

Crime

Crime is a naturally occurring phenomenon and is as old as the human race. It is defined as an act that is incompatible with the accepted norms of any particular society. Since crime is a natural occurrence, it can not be eradicated, but those responsible for managing crime (prevention and detection of crime) are only responsible for reducing crime to a tolerable level [7].

Crime has also been defined in many ways: some studies described the crime as an act or omission that renders a person liable to punishment for an act or omission. Others regard it as an illegal act; an act punishable by law. While some claim that criminality is an act, default, or behavior that is harmful to the society, the execution of which renders the individual liable to penalty by law [7].

Categories of Crimes

Crimes are graded in ways, particularly based on the severity of the crime [8], [7]. These classes are as follows:

- i) **Crime against persons** – assault, murder, kidnapping, sexual attacks, etc.
- ii) **Crime against property** – arson, burglary, automobile theft, willful damage, embezzlement, forgery, fraud, vandalism, etc
- iii) **Crimes against private and public morality** – disorderly conduct, gambling, prostitution, public drunkenness, vagrancy, having no permanent residence, no visible means of subsistence, etc.
- iv) **Organized crime** – Gangersterism, racketeering, advanced fee fraud, etc.
- v) **White-collar crimes** – stock market swindlers, cheating in payment of taxes [8], [7].

Characteristics of Crime

- a) Crime is an act inconsistent with the norms acceptable in any society.

- b) The meaning of crime differs from society to society. For instance, what is a crime in the USA may not be a crime in Nigeria and vice versa.
- c) Crime affects the community as a whole and is different from civil wrong which affects only the parties involved.
- d) In Nigeria, crime is a wrong against the state and that is why a victim of a crime is only a prosecution witness.
- e) Crime is time-based. What is a crime today that might not be a crime tomorrow?

Offender Tracking

Better technology for offender tracking has the potential to increase public safety by making information on offenders easier to share and utilize. However, the use of the technology by law enforcement agencies must be balanced against individual rights and the resulting public perception of the activity [7], [9].

Intelligence Gathering

However, according to Nweke (2006), intelligence collection in the area of crime reduction and identification involves capturing, capturing, compiling, storing, assessing, and disseminating knowledge in respect of a crime being committed or about to be committed with a view to detecting or preventing its execution. This is a confidential compilation of information, after constant surveillance of the actions and behavior of offenders and disruptive parts of society [7], [10].

The collection of information is extremely relevant in the avoidance and investigation of crime worldwide. This is in appreciation of this unique role that organizations such as the CIA, FIB, KGB have been set up. In Nigeria, we have State Security Services (SSS), National Intelligence Agency (NIA), Criminal Intelligence Office (CIB), Criminal Investigation Department (CID) [7].

Sources of Intelligence Information

- 1) A thorough analysis of newspapers and broadcasts may suggest crime patterns and intentions. Officers and people are therefore aware of the value of the press.
- 2) **Informant:** An Informants are extremely valuable to intelligence forces, whether they be temporary informants, permanent informants, or informants beyond the reach of the aim.
- 3) **Surveillance:** Many of the intelligence gatherings that help prevent and detect crime are acquired through surveillance. Information received in the continuous monitoring of persons, vehicles, places or objects shall be developed into intelligent reports which serve as a guide [9].
- 4) **Observation and Description Techniques:** An Observation is the capacity to pick up the expression of the senses (what is perceived, smelled, smelt, felt, or tested) and explanation is the ability to describe what has been experienced in depth from memory. Both assist in identifying and stopping crime.
- 5) **Investigation:** This is a standard method that is used to gather or obtain information on events that have occurred or are about to happen to establish the truth [7]. The steps involve:
 - a. Search for information
 - b. Use of available information to get evidence
 - c. Interpretation of available information
 - d. Use of a set of methods to achieve the desired objective
 - e. The conclusion reached after evaluating the information.

Crime Prevention and Detection

Through a community standpoint, crime reduction is the easiest and most effective operation that law enforcement officers will conduct. If crimes are successfully prevented before they occur, the costs of social and the suffering associated with the effects of crime are completely avoided. Crime prevention and detection are closely interwoven, but both concepts are not the same. You may deter the execution of a crime by identifying the anticipatory actions early enough before the commission of a crime [8], [7].

Crime Prevention: As is the case under the Indian Police Act, it describes a situation where crimes are discovered and thus prevented before the actual commission. According to the Australian Criminology Institute, crime prevention applies to a variety of initiatives adopted by people, societies, corporations, non-governmental organizations, and all levels of government to tackle different social and environmental causes that raise the likelihood of violence, disturbance, and victimization [8], [7].

Crime Detection: Relation is provided to the investigating abilities of law enforcement agencies to detect the conduct of the crime at all points and to be able to locate the persona suspects engaged in the commission of the crime. Crime identification requires the compilation and processing of relevant details linked to the crime in question. Examples include eye-witness evidence, victim testimony, interviewee, observation, etc., which are highly correlated to ensure the reliability or accuracy of the evidence [7].

However, it should be stated, according to Nweke (2006) [6], that both concepts are working together for better as envisaged in section 4 of the Indian Police Act. This inference is necessary because you can only deter crime if you learn of its nature and foresee it; so you learn of the presence of a crime without being a party to it, because you sense it. Therefore, the avoidance of a crime may and is typically followed by the identification of a crime [7], [8], [11].

Community Role in Crime Prevention and Detection

It should be noted that without the cooperation and support of the public, there will be no dividend from the efforts of the police to curb crime. Citizens do not recognize that they are fully liable for law enforcement and have legislative rights and responsibilities to carry out this duty. Of starters, an eye witness of a crime might probably prefer to turn the other way than to fulfill what could be called his civic responsibility, if not his legal obligation to supply the police with the required evidence in his hands [7]

Individuals and societies owe a special duty to themselves and to the state to be conscious of their privileges of protection. This right is exemplified when you anticipate and prevent the actions of others from harming you. That is their moral and ethical responsibility to deter violence. It can also be remembered that crime reduction is not accomplished by retaliatory acts or proactive abuse, but by timely notification to law enforcement officers[7].

Finally, members of society are expected to assist a police officer in the performance of his duties. The law provides that if a citizen is called upon to help and support a police officer if, when doing his duties, is attacked or resisted, or is in danger of being assaulted or resisted, and that person refuses or neglects to assist in doing so, he shall be guilty of an offense ...” [7].

The ICT

ICT is an umbrella that encompasses any electronic tool or communication device that includes; radio, television, cellular phones, video cameras, calculators, computer networks, software and hardware, satellite systems and so on, as well as a variety of services and apps, such as video conferencing, online lectures and distance education. With increased accessibility to ICT technology, a major change has taken place from readiness to practice ICT for a variety of purposes. These revolutionary technologies have the greatest potential to achieve the goals of good governance in India. Everything from business to governance is changing [5], [1].

Police and other security personnel are also today faced with increasing pressure from all stakeholders, not only the media and the public, to detect, investigate and prevent crime, but also from their employees, for efficient working and service conditions. ICT is the only solution to make the police work more effective [1].

Uses of ICT in the Indian Police Force

Policing is a very dynamic and responsive task that involves the incorporation of many data sources in a brief period. ICT tools help the police to deliver better and timely services to the economy, efficiency, and effectiveness [1].

ICT-Rich Environment

Regarding even what could be found in a traditional physical crime scene, far more than forensic proof is likely to be usable. There is always going to be an explosion of technologies on the scene. For examples:

- Devices to prevent crime and/or warn that a crime might be about to take place, e.g. an intrusion warning.
- Equipment for recording a crime committed, e.g. Uh, CCTV
- Equipment inside the crime scene that could include new visual information related to the crime itself, the victim or the suspect, e.g. cell phone, iPhone, SatNav, etc.
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- Equipment introduced to the site, either a crime scene analyst or probably a forensic scientist, to enable location, identification, documentation, examination (both probable and real-time research) and dissemination of information, e.g. by the usage of crime lighting, video cameras, laser scanners, 360o photography, sensor test, etc.
- Software to better locate the perpetrator(s), e.g. remote smartphone fingerprint detection and identification technology, Automated Plate Number Identification (APNI), etc. [3].

ICT Utilization in Crime Identifications

It is quite quick to recognize an individual via ICT. Security Officers can use a variety of methods to track down a suspect to combat crime and preserving law and order. Any type of electronic communication the individual chooses; it is an essential means of electronic identification. [1], [9].

As previously mentioned, equipment at the crime scene will also be utilized to collect details in real-time about the incident at the moment when the incident is conducted. These details can refer to the crime itself, the victim, or the suspect of the crime [3]. For example, consider the following:

- 1) **Electronic Transport (E-Transport)** Big transport-related operations can be done conveniently via mobile technologies. The E-Transport component includes a range of things such as registration of all forms of motor vehicles, issue of driving licenses, issue of permits for medium and heavy vehicles, recovery of taxes and costs through cash and bank coupons and emission management by inspections, etc. [1], [3], [9].
- 2) **Online Verification and Fingerprints Reader:** Biometric devices and fingerprint scanners are now helping to uphold the legislation and enhance the activities of the police. Biometric technology helps in the online verification and recognition of people from different geographical locations. This offers reliable details to the accused party and creates room for swift decision-making on relevant security concerns [1], [3], [9].
- 3) **Automatic Number Plate Recognition** – Used by law enforcement across the country to determine the location and movement of vehicles (and occupants) of interest, both in real-time and retrospectively; and (through linked databases) used to facilitate the identification of criminals and

criminal action, e.g. driving illegally, tax or MOT; location of stolen vehicles, etc. In certain instances, such 'hits' can even direct the police to uncover even more serious forms of illegal conduct [1], [3], [7].

- 4) **CCTV (Closed Circuit Television):** Used by a wide range of stakeholders, from police, transport providers and networks, city councils, businesses, householders, etc., to capture footage and images related to potential criminal activity and to facilitate the identification of the offender(s); and also to act as a deterrent. We are all too well acquainted with the extent to which this technology has pervaded our work, social and community environments; and equally well acquainted with the 'mug shots' that have arisen, which have been circulated by the police or by charities such as Crime Stoppers, to the public via TV, web-sites or the press [1], [3], [8], [9], [12].
- 5) **Mobile Phone:** There are already millions of cell phone users in the UK. Many owners also can record, intentionally or unknowingly, crime-related details; and they do have the opportunity to send such details (real-time), via social networking platforms such as Linked-in and Twitter, as well as through YouTube, etc. The captured information may include 'video' or photographic images taken as a crime, e.g. footage taken during the London riots that recorded the crimes being committed, or information stored on the phone that could be used to record a previous event, e.g. pictures showing the location of the crime, layout and 'contents' at a recorded (and verifiable) date and time [1], [3], [8], [9], [12].
- 6) **Human Resource Management:** HRM is a very essential task to maintain the available human resources for the accomplishment of goals. The strength of a police force is distributed, according to requirements of the department, divisions, sub-divisions, districts. Bunyard (1978) describes that ICT has the greatest ability to add benefits to the recruiting, procurement, preparation, the advancement of police officers, and to monitor personnel wages and allowances [5]. In the police selection process, the use of ICT starts with an advertisement, filling out forms, written test data, date of interview of suitable candidates and eligible candidate's candidates, etc. In doing that, the police force will ensure that employees are adequately qualified to operate with the new technologies [5].
- 7) **Police-Public Interface:** E-Police should help build the trust of the resident. The first phase in the usage of ICTs will be an interaction between the police and the public. The police are the body responsible for securing the life and property of the public. The ICT public will be able to view data on the progress of their complaints and the police will be able to provide feedback on them. Significant activities can be carried out web such as online foreigner registration, stolen vehicle database, passport verification, and live updates and alternative routes for traffic control, etc.. This will help minimize work and reduce redundancy in the work of the police. This will increase transparency and provide services between the limited timeframe [1].
- 8) **Real-time Information Access:** In a large geographical area which is very hard to check and administer the Global Positioning System (GPS) and Geographical Information System (GIS) are used to track the information about a particular area and movement of suspected and terrorists etc. with the available data and video. The available information provides the ability to organize all the events for better tracking, recording, and taking action. This system allows police officers to take preventive measures. GPS is extremely helpful for monitoring a stolen car, allowing choices on traffic flow and reducing overcrowding, and offering intelligence about when police units are close to reacting to an incident [1], [9], [12].
- 9) **RFID (Radio Frequency Identification):** Recently, automated tracking methods have become popular in the provision of several services. They can have details on individuals, companies, and items. It is a technology that uses radio waves to transmit data from an electronic tag or label attached to an object via a reader to identify and track the movement of material across the country. Such equipment is utilized by police departments so that transit networks may be checked to deter the transportation of illegal goods which could affect public safety. The information on the tag is stored electronically. The precise position of each police officer could be more useful for the provision of police services. Such a device appears to be an effective resource for gathering and presenting details on the position of officers [1], [12].

Both of these instances represent the potential of a device customer to collect information or facts relevant to a crime at the moment that it is conducted. Furthermore, it also greatly adds additional 'people' to the crime scene investigation, i.e. it is not just the crime scene detective who collects and reports information relevant to the incident. These agents, and the use of their technology, are introducing new functionality,

new roles and, of course, new challenges to the criminal investigation process, particularly in dealing with digital evidence resulting from their involvement in the crime scene [1], [3].

Cyber Security

Cybersecurity includes the defense of confidential individuals and company details by avoidance, monitoring, and reaction to numerous cyber-attacks. Cyber Security effectively protects your private information by responding, detecting, and preventing attacks [9], [13].

A) Protecting Your Privacy

- a. **Privacy policy:** Until sending your name, email address, or other personal details to the website, please check the Privacy Policy of the website [13].
- b. **Evidence that your information is being encrypted:** To protect attackers from hijacking your information, any personal information submitted online should be encrypted. Many sites use the SSL or secure socket layer to encrypt information [13].

B) How Can We Protect?

- a. **Keep software up-to-date:** If the vendor releases patches for software running your device, install them as soon as possible. Installing them will prevent the attack from taking advantage of them [13].
- b. **Use good passwords:** Select passwords that are hard to guess for the thieves. Do not choose options that will allow your computer to remember your passwords [13].
- c. **Disable remote connectivity:** Some PDA's and phones are wirelessly connected innovations, such as Bluetooth, that can be used to connect to other devices or computers. You should disable these features when they are not in use [13].

C) The Changing Nature of Cybercrime

New trends in cybercrime are emerging all the time, with the global economy costing billions of dollars. In the past, cybercrime has been committed primarily by individuals or small groups [13]. Today, we see criminal groups collaborating with illegally inclined experts to conduct cybercrime, mostly to finance such illicit acts. Highly sophisticated, these cyber-crime networks put together people from across the world to conduct crimes to an unparalleled scale in real-time [13].

Criminal organizations are rapidly moving to the Web to promote their operations and increase their income in the shortest period available. Crimes themselves are not necessarily new – such as theft, fraud, illegal gambling, the sale of counterfeit medicines – but they are evolving in line with the opportunities presented online and are therefore becoming more widespread and harmful [13].

D) INTERPOL'S Role

INTERPOL is dedicated to being a regional organizing agency for the investigation and prevention of international criminals through its INTERPOL Global Complex for Innovation (IGCI) in Singapore. The INTERPOL Digital Crime Center is a key component of this new state-of-the-art research and development facility. This new program offers constructive research into new areas and the latest training methods and coordinates field operations [13].

Challenges Fronting by ICT Security Officers

Criminals remain a step forward for the police to make use of the latest technology, including ICT. Indian police in the face of many problems in maintaining law and order, such as:

- Lack of appropriate and effective policing procedures, very bad working standards, lack of professional advancement services for a significant range of constabularies, following the findings of a variety of commissions, commissions.

- Lack of integrated information systems for the smooth functioning of the police force.
- Lack of capacity to share information with other related national level and national level agencies;
- Several reports with the same details and insufficient capacity to interpret knowledge attributable to specific positions and analytical skills; [1].

It makes it important for the Indian police to further train its staff to keep up with evolving times and to cope with the issues of today's day. Such issues call for certain ideas that can be addressed [1].

Solutions for the Improvement

Some proposals for improving the functioning of the police force can be identified. Society should become a safe environment where every person can live without fear [1].

- The on-line integration of all the information required for the police service also saves time for the police, so that technical skills and knowledge are required for the police to make the information available online.
- Most police activities require information processing so that the police need to invest in ICTs to increase their capacity to store and process large volumes of data.
- The main emphasis in the new era is on customer service and performance measures. ICT in the police sector should therefore be designed to meet the information requirements of the new management system.
- For accountability purposes, the police department should regularly transmit crime and accident data to road traffic authorities and insurance companies so that they can act proactively rather than reactively.

Such recommendations can be proven useful in regulating the crime and maintenance of law and order in the community. To meet the problems of the coming years it is important to have a police force that is up-to-date with the knowledge of ICTs in routine work [1].

Conclusion

Collaborative ICT-enabled intervention is used to direct government agencies on the road to greater productivity and transparency in strengthening protection. In some cases, it is by naming and shaming, as if the website publicly documents the police soliciting bribes. In other cases, ICTs offer a way to measure the severity of the situation, whether it is in rural, urban, or online crime. ICT is the lifeblood of crime reduction and identification. ICT capabilities play a vital role in supporting all processes for preventing and detecting crime and enabling the delivery of police services. ICT applied in the context of crime detection, prevention, law enforcement, and signals intelligence is dedicated to alleviating the problem of crime. ICT methods may theoretically be used to popular, track, and even deter violence over the coming years. Both efforts to deter and track crime will be underpinned by comprehensive ICT-enabled.

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